

THE ROLE OF UKRAINIAN LITERARY TRANSLATION IN CHINA IN PROMOTING LITERARY DISSEMINATION

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Abstract. *The paper aims to identify the importance of Ukrainian literary translation in China with regard to promoting literary dissemination. It has been demonstrated that literary cooperation between China and Ukraine must continue to play a powerful accelerator role in the spirit of pragmatic cooperation between the two countries.*

Key words: *China, Ukraine, Literature, Literary Translation, Literary Dissemination.*

Аннотация. *Цель статьи – определить важность украинского художественного перевода в Китае в содействии распространения литературы. Доказано, что в контексте новых возможностей и новых вызовов литературное сотрудничество между Китаем и Украиной должно не только продолжать играть важную роль ускорителя в духе прагматичного сотрудничества между двумя странами, но и стать катализатором углубленного развития отношений между двумя культурами.*

Ключевые слова: *Китай, Украина, литература, литературный перевод, распространение литературы.*

In the era of complex and changeable geopolitical relations, frequent conflicts, and information warfare, we can observe that many traditional methods that affect international relations have dysfunction. When it comes to cultural identity and culture itself, it is worth pointing out that culture is now regarded as a new way to strengthen national interests. In this case, literary translation becomes the most convenient channel, because literature is an indispensable part of most people's daily lives. Moreover, literary translation makes it easier for people to participate in cross-cultural communication.

According to Maitland, the essence of literature is to cross the boundaries of language, culture, and civilization [2, 38.]. Furthermore, Domansky believes a literary text puts a person "at the crossroads" of dialogue, absorbing the existential

meaning of a given culture and that literary works are presented in the form of peculiar psychological formations. He argues further that the dialogical relations with the characters, the author and various epochs contributes greatly to culture itself [5, 31.].

Literary translation plays an important role in the process of cultural exchange and in the storage and dissemination of important social information. The reality of life, the concepts and objects of the environment and the facts of culture can be used as information of social significance. According to Gholami, all cultural objects are reflected in language in one way or another. Words (or other language units) name cultural objects (artifacts) to obtain additional symbolic meanings, which are not always fixed by dictionaries, and can convey new meanings [4, 775]. This is especially obvious when changing (at least in part) cultural norms. Gholami explains further that literary works as cultural objects can be viewed from three aspects. First of all, literary works reflect the entire life of the people, including culture as its most important component. Secondly, language as the material of literary works is one of the most important cultural phenomena. Finally, literary works as works of art are themselves the products of culture [4, 776].

For more than 100 years, thanks to the translation and dissemination of literature by translation, Chinese readers have been able to read world classics through a steady stream of excellent translations and absorb the achievements of outstanding foreign civilizations. They also promote outstanding Chinese literary works overseas, so that the world can learn more about China today. It can be said that literary translation is working with contemporary literary creation to not only explore and create contemporary Chinese grammar and aesthetic principles with new characteristics, but also promote outstanding literary works that carry the unique spiritual feelings, cultural accumulation and ideological connotations of Chinese people into the world pattern, and gain more recognition and respect in exchanges and interactions with the world [1,169].

Cai (translator and professor at Zhejiang University of Finance and Economics) states that "...as long as people exist for a day, the desire to express will not stop, and literature is one of the most important forms of expression". He further adds that the value of literary creation and translation lies in this kind of penetration that reaches the soul." [3, 3]

Literary works directly relate to culture and store information about history, national psychology, and national behaviour. Reading foreign novels can be comparable to the process of cultural exchange, because the author and the reader are representatives of different cultures. Literary works are a true combination of linguistics and cultural research. Literature is a kind of dialogue between the author

and potential readers. At the same time, when creating artistic texts, the author focuses on fixed demonstration models that reflect the world in a particular culture. The art of the reader's interpretation of the text lies in being able to see the invisible, not lying on the surface, and contains the psychological layer of consciousness, that is, seeing certain personality traits of the author of the text, and the influence of his worldview imposed by the external environment on the character of the work. However, Ostapenko states, that it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the recipient (reader), because the specific details of his consciousness depend not only on personal experience, but also on the particularity of national culture, which determines the choice of text interpretation [6, 223].

As part of foreign literature in China, Ukrainian literature is one of the key areas for the development of Sino-Ukrainian cultural exchanges on the basis of the “Belt and Road” cooperation initiative. After the efforts of several generations of Chinese and Ukrainian experts, the works of Ukrainian writers have always been within the vision of Chinese translators, researchers and readers. Chinese readers are more familiar with Ukrainian classics, Ukrainian modern literature and Soviet. Although Chinese readers have only been exposed to Ukrainian literature since the beginning of the 20th century, important writers and masterpieces in Ukrainian literature, as well as most classic works, have been introduced to Chinese readers. As part of Soviet literature, Ukrainian literature has had a significant influence on China. However, with the collapse of the Soviet Union, the original influence of Ukrainian literature was almost lost. The interest of the younger generation of Chinese readers in Ukrainian literature is considerably less than older generations.

Since some cultural elements of Ukrainian language, namely proverbs, sayings, dialect expressions, etc., will be lost in the process of translation, from a linguistic point of view, literary works as a tool for disseminating Ukrainian culture are not very effective. In this case, a more expressive example can be given from the perspective of the existence and transmission of cultural elements in literary works to the reader. Regardless of the genre, subject matter, and writing time of the work, Chinese readers can always be familiar with the Ukrainian culture on the surface of literary works. This can be a detailed description of Ukrainian customs and traditions, such as wedding ceremonies, New Year and Easter celebrations, Christian weddings, baptism ceremonies, descriptions of national costumes and delicacies. Whether it is the 19th-century works of Taras Shevchenko and Mykola Gogol or modern Ukrainian literature, these elements always exist in the works because they are the immutable cultural elements of the Ukrainian nation. In addition, readers who can analyze the works and plots can fully understand the national character of the Ukrainian people. Through detailed analysis, Chinese readers can also understand the social compo-

nents of Ukrainian culture, including the behaviour of different strata of the Ukrainian population and their attitudes towards each other, the attitudes of the Ukrainian people towards money and other social factors.

Literary translation of Ukrainian works makes it easy for Chinese readers to discover the differences between Ukrainian and Chinese culture. These differences are mainly manifested in the different status of men and women in the family, the degree of feminism spreading in society, society's attitude towards doctors and teachers, favourite leisure activities and attitudes toward the balance of work and personal life. However, on the other hand, people can also find cultural elements that are very close to the two cultures of China and Ukraine, namely the importance of family in a person's life, love for the motherland and respect for elders. These social themes are most evident in modern Ukrainian literary works, which should now become the main aspect of spreading Ukrainian culture in China. Unfortunately, although modern Ukrainian literature has played a huge role in promoting Ukrainian culture, there is not works available in China. But there is no doubt that both parties have great potential to spread the works of such contemporary Ukrainian authors. It is hoped that in the near future, the works of writers such as Ivan Baidak, Artem Cech, Pavel Kolobchuk, and Max Kidruk will appear not only in the West, but also on the shelves of Chinese bookstores. In addition, on the basis of disseminating literary works, various special events can also be held in China, including meetings between Ukrainian writers and Chinese readers, forums between Ukrainian and Chinese writers, and special literary events in Chinese schools, universities, and bookstores to familiarize Chinese people with Ukrainian literary works and authors.

China and Ukraine are two countries with deep literary traditions. There is also a long history of literary exchanges between China and Ukraine. Some Chinese and their descendants who grew up in the atmosphere of brotherly friendship between the people of China and the Soviet Union in the mid-to-late last century have all kinds of love and nostalgia for Ukrainian literature. The literary exchanges between China and Ukraine are carried out under the unremitting efforts of translators, as well as other translating institutions and agencies which are keen on cultural exchanges and are interested in establishing ties between China and Ukraine. In order to ensure the effectiveness and high level of translations of literary works, it is necessary to focus on promoting the high-quality translation and publication of important Chinese and Ukrainian literary works. Today, in China, the number of translators engaged in the translation of Ukrainian literature is significantly smaller than that of the older generation. In this regard, the Chinese and Ukrainian literary circles should take some effective measures, such as offering courses for translators of literary translation. At present, the common problem faced by students studying Chinese in Ukrainian

universities is that traditional teaching methods dominate, relying too much on textbooks, and the evaluation method is mainly written exams which leads to a lack of practical application. To emphasize the effectiveness of talent training, we can start from the following aspects. The first is to optimize the curriculum system and establish an education system focusing on the development of applied talents. This will result in an increase in the share of practical training in the fields of interpretation and translation, as well as economics and trade, and increase the number of practical training courses so that theory can respond to practice, and knowledge and ability can grow in parallel. Secondly, improve the teaching methods. The main interactive learning model should be adopted. The allocation of time in the classroom increases students' practice time, which increases the effectiveness of learning. Finally, practical awareness should be cultivated and practical opportunities should be provided. If teachers encourage students to actively participate in a number of activities in order to use the language more in practice, this will create a good practical application environment, and allow students to demonstrate their abilities and improve their practical skills. It is necessary to give students the opportunity to explore and use Chinese in many various ways.

Undoubtedly, the “One Belt One Road“ initiative has opened up a new field for the development of Sino-Ukrainian literary diplomacy. Historical opportunities should be seized to improve the curriculum system for teaching Ukrainian in Chinese universities and Chinese in Ukrainian universities. The closer mutual cooperation in the economic, political and cultural fields between the two countries has increased the demand for Ukrainian-speaking and Chinese-speaking experts, including experts in the field of literature. On the basis of the “One Belt One Road“ initiative, we can hold activities dedicated to the translation of Sino-Ukrainian literature and the publication of books, hold Sino-Ukrainian literary and scientific forums, and set up awards for outstanding translation works. It can also promote a special project for mutual translation of classical Chinese and Ukrainian literature and modern and contemporary literary works, and reach an agreement on the content and quantity of mutual translation of literary works between the two countries in the next few years. Sino-Ukrainian literary exchanges should be consolidated at the level of academic research institutions and the governments of the two countries. Moreover, there should be more frequent cooperation between publishers, translators, and governmental cultural and diplomatic departments of the two countries, so that Sino-Ukrainian literary exchanges can reach a new level, with a view to vastly increase the cultural exchanges and literary dissemination and reading between the two countries.

Conclusion. Literary translation is one of the important ways of cultural communication. Because literary works can result in readers valuing other cultures

more highly as they become more familiar with certain characteristics and details. Strengthening Sino-Ukrainian cultural exchanges can promote the common development of Sino-Ukrainian literature. Ukrainian literary works are very rich in forms. When reading Ukrainian literary works, Chinese readers can broaden their research horizons, enrich their innovative thinking, further understand Ukrainian culture, and strengthen exchanges and communications between China and Ukraine. In this case, the translation of Ukrainian literature and its dissemination in China occupy an important position, which opens up the possibility of learning Ukrainian culture. The dissemination of high-quality Ukrainian literary translation in Chinese libraries, bookstores and the Internet, the increase in the attractiveness of Ukrainian literature to Chinese readers, the holding of literary evenings and exhibitions, and the study of Ukrainian literary works in Chinese schools and universities are the scope of influence of Sino-Ukrainian cultural exchanges. Therefore, in the contradictory and complex geopolitical and socio-cultural reality, the principle of cultural exchange through literary translation seems to be an important aspect of realizing the development of relations between Ukraine and China.

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